

1 **Wheat stem rust back in Europe: Diversity, prevalence and impact on host resistance**

2 Mehran Patpour^{a†}, Mogens S. Hovmøller^{a*†}, Julian Rodriguez-Algaba^a, Biagio Randazzo^b, Dolors
3 Villegas^c, Vladimir P. Shamanin^c, Anna Berlin^c, Kerstin Flath^f, Pawel Czembor^g, Alena Hanzalova^h,
4 Svetlana Slikováⁱ, Ekaterina S. Skolotneva^j, Yue Jin^k, Les Szabo^k, Kevin J.G. Meyer^l, Romain Valade^m,
5 Tine Thach^a, Jens G. Hansen^a, Annemarie F. Justesen^{*a}

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7 ^a Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University, Slagelse, Denmark

8 ^b Società Semplice Agricola Randazzo (S.A.R.), Baucina, Italy

9 ^c Institute for Food and Agricultural Research and Technology, (IRTA), Sustainable Field Crops
10 Programme, Lleida, Spain

11 ^d Omsk State Agrarian University, Omsk, Russia

12 ^e Swedish Agricultural University, Department of Forest Mycology and Plant Pathology. Uppsala,
13 Sweden

14 ^f Julius Kühn-Institut, Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants, Institute for Plant Protection in
15 Field Crops and Grassland, Kleinmachnow, Germany

16 ^g Plant Breeding & Acclimatization Institute, Radzikow, Blonie, Poland

17 ^h Crop Research Institute, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding Methods, Praha Ruzyně, Czech
18 Republic

19 ⁱ National Agricultural and Food Centre, Bratislava, Slovakia

20 ^j Institute of Cytology and Genetics, Russian Academy of Sciences, Novosibirsk, Russia

21 ^k USDA-ARS Cereal Disease Laboratory, University of Minnesota, St. Paul, USA

22 ^l Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, UR BIOGER Thiverval-Grignon, France

23 ^m ARVALIS Institut du Végétal, Boigneville, France

24

25 †These authors have contributed equally to this work and share first authorship

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28 * **Correspondence:** Mogens Støvring Hovmøller (mogens.hovmoller@agro.au.dk); Annemarie Fejer
29 Justesen (annemariefejer.justesen@agro.au.dk)

30 **Abstract**

31 The objective of this study was to investigate the re-emergence of a previously important crop pathogen
32 in Europe, *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici*, causing wheat stem rust. The pathogen has been insignificant
33 in Europe for more than 60 years, but since 2016 causing epidemics on both durum wheat and bread
34 wheat in local areas in southern Europe, and additional outbreaks in Central- and West Europe. The
35 prevalence of three distinct genotypes/races in many areas, Clade III-B (TTRTF), Clade IV-B (TKTTF)
36 and Clade IV-F (TKKTF), suggested clonal reproduction and additional evolution by mutation within
37 these. None of these genetic groups and races, which likely originated from exotic incursions, were
38 detected in Europe prior to 2016. A fourth genetic group, Clade VIII, detected in Germany (2013), was
39 observed in several years in Central- and East Europe. Tests of representative European wheat varieties
40 with prevalent races revealed high level of susceptibility. In contrast, high diversity with respect to
41 virulence and Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) markers were detected in local populations on cereals and
42 grasses in proximity to the alternate host, *Berberis* species, in Spain and Sweden. A geographical
43 distant population from Omsk and Novosibirsk in western Siberia also revealed high genetic diversity,
44 but clearly different from current European populations. The presence of *Sr31*-virulence in multiple
45 and highly diverse races in local populations in Spain and Siberia stress that virulence may emerge
46 independently when large geographical areas and time spans are considered and that *Sr31*-virulence is
47 not unique to Ug99. All isolates of the Spanish populations, collected from wheat, rye and grass
48 species, were successfully recovered on wheat, which underline the plasticity of host barriers within *P.*
49 *graminis*. The study demonstrated successful alignment of results from different laboratories based on
50 SNP and SSR genotyping, respectively, as well as race phenotyping, which allowed us to line up with
51 previous European and international studies of wheat stem rust. Our results suggest that *Berberis*
52 species may return as an important component in the epidemiology of wheat stem rust in Europe. New
53 breeding efforts to increase stem rust resistance in European wheat germplasm is strongly
54 recommended.

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60 **1 Introduction**

61 Stem rust on wheat, caused by the basidiomycete *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pgt*) Eriks. & E.
62 Henn., has historically been considered a main threat for wheat production globally (Singh et al., 2016).
63 The disease, which is also known as black rust, became less prevalent in Europe during the 2nd half of
64 the 20th century, due to a combination of efforts to eradicate common barberry (*Berberis vulgaris*), the
65 alternate host for multiple *formae speciales* of *Pgt* (Lind, 1915; Stakman, 1923; Hermansen, 1968), as
66 well as advances in plant breeding and plant disease management. Nevertheless, stem rust persisted as
67 a potential threat mainly in warmer wheat growing areas in Central and Eastern Europe (Bartoš et al.,
68 1996). In Africa, the situation has changed since 1999 by the emergence of a new race group, termed
69 ‘Ug99’, which carries virulence to stem rust resistance *Sr31*, thereby leaving many wheat cultivars
70 susceptible to stem rust (Pretorius et al., 2000; Singh et al., 2011). Since then, stem rust of different
71 genetic groups and races have emerged in East Africa, e.g., the ‘Digalu’ race (TKTTF), which resulted
72 in epidemics in Ethiopia in 2013 and following years (Olivera et al., 2015).

73 In 2013, stem rust reappeared on several wheat cultivars at several locations in Germany (Olivera Firpo
74 et al., 2017) along with sporadic incidences in southern Denmark, eastern Sweden and the United
75 Kingdom (Lewis et al., 2018). A more widespread outbreak was reported from Sicily in Italy, 2016,
76 where thousands of hectares of both bread and durum wheat were affected (Bhattacharya, 2017).
77 Preliminary analyses of infected plant samples from Sicily suggested the presence of a new race in
78 Europe, TTRTF (termed TTTTF in Bhattacharya (2017)), which carried virulence to *Sr13b* of
79 particular relevance for durum wheat (Patpour et al., 2020). These events were followed by the
80 detection of stem rust on late maturing wheat and barley in local areas in Sweden in 2017, characterized
81 by cool temperatures and an unusual wet growing season (Berlin, 2017). Since then, stem rust has been
82 observed every year on wheat, barley and rye in these areas (Kjellström, 2021). Earlier studies in
83 Sweden have shown that stem rust on oat and rye reproduce asexually on the cereal host and sexually
84 on the alternate host, *B. vulgaris* (Berlin et al., 2012).

85 A new initiative to establish a European early-warning system for wheat rust diseases, RustWatch, was
86 launched in May 2018, including the coordination of national wheat rust surveillance and rust
87 resistance breeding efforts (<http://agro.au.dk/forskning/projekter/rustwatch/>). This initiative builds on
88 the achievements of the Global Rust Reference Center (GRRC) at Aarhus University, Denmark, and
89 the Borlaug Global Rust Initiative, which was launched in 2008 in response to the emergence of the

90 stem rust race Ug99 and multiple variants (McIntosh and Pretorius, 2011). The role of the alternate
91 host in the epidemiology of *Pgt* in Europe at present time was an important part of the RustWatch
92 initiative, following the increase in prevalence in at least Sweden and the United Kingdom, after the
93 lapse in legislation about planting and eradication of common barberry in the 1990s (Berlin et al., 2012;
94 Saunders et al., 2019).

95 In this study, we investigated whether stem rust outbreaks in Europe since 2016 could be connected to
96 a local outbreak in Germany in 2013, and to which extent the populations were influenced by exotic
97 incursions from outside Europe as opposed to evolution by mutation and/or sexual recombination in
98 local populations in proximity to *Berberis* spp. These hypotheses were explored by extensive sampling
99 of stem rust from new outbreaks in agricultural areas in Europe as well as in local areas in Sweden and
100 Spain, where the alternate host has been documented, and from a distant wheat growing area in western
101 Siberia, Russia. All samples were genotyped to investigate genetic variability and relatedness, and
102 subsets were race typed to investigate phenotypic diversity for virulence and epidemic potential on
103 European wheat varieties.

104 **2 Materials and methods**

105 **2.1 Collection and recovery of wheat stem rust samples**

106 A total of 479 samples of stem rust from mainly wheat, occasionally other cereals, and grasses, were
107 collected from 17 European countries and western Siberia, Russia (Table 1). The number of samples
108 varied across years and locations, largely reflecting sporadic and variable occurrence and sampling
109 efforts of wheat stem rust. Twenty-five reference isolates of diverse geographical origin, including
110 isolates representing the German outbreak in 2013, and DNA samples hosted by the USDA ARS Cereal
111 Disease Lab, Minnesota, USA, were included to ensure alignment with previous studies and
112 genotyping methodologies (Table 2) (Olivera Firpo et al., 2017; Lewis et al., 2018; Szabo et al., 2022).

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114 Mailing and shipment of samples followed the protocol by (Olivera et al., 2015). Most of the samples
115 from western Siberia were collected during a surveillance trip in 2016 and additional samples from the
116 same areas were submitted to GRRC in 2017. Samples from Sweden were part of a comprehensive
117 stem rust survey in 2018-2019, following the first detection of a sexual *Pgt* population on barley and
118 wheat in proximity to common barberry in the autumn of 2017. Samples from Spain were collected
119 from cereal and grass hosts in areas in close proximity to indigenous subspecies of the alternate host,

120 *B. vulgaris*, and in contrasting areas where the alternate host was not present. Samples from France,
121 2021, were part of a national stem rust survey initiated as an early reaction to the widespread
122 appearance of the disease in June-July 2021.

123 Recovery was facilitated by placing stem and/or leaves on moist filter papers in petri dishes under
124 humid conditions at 18°C for 1-2 days to promote the formation of urediniospores. Thereafter, the
125 infected tissue of each sample was gently rubbed on the adaxial side of seedling leaves of the
126 universally stem rust susceptible wheat lines Morocco, Line E and McNair 701. The seedlings were
127 grown in pots, 12-15 plants per pot, and treated with 5 ml of 0.5% Antergon MH180 (Nordisk Alkali,
128 Randers, Denmark) to regulate plant growth and enhance spore production. The inoculated seedlings
129 were misted with water and incubated in a dew chamber at 18°C in darkness for 24 h under high relative
130 humidity (RH), after which they were transferred to spore-proof greenhouse cabins set to 20°C during
131 day/18°C during night with a 16 h photoperiod of natural light and supplemental sodium light (200
132 $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1}\text{m}^{-2}$) and 8 h darkness. Plants were watered automatically with added micronutrients for 10
133 min every 12 h. The pots were covered with cellophane bags (Helmut Schmidt Verpackungsfolien
134 GmbH, Königswinter, Germany) before onset of sporulation to avoid cross contamination between
135 samples. Urediniospores from each sample were harvested, dried, and stored in a liquid nitrogen cryo
136 container (-196°C), or freezer (-80°C), until further use.

137 **2.2 DNA extraction**

138 Genomic DNA was extracted from leaf segments, typically 1-2 cm, containing single pustules of *Pgt*
139 taken from multiplication pots or directly from infected stem segments of incoming samples. The
140 specimens were dried and stored in a desiccator for 24-48 h. Prior to DNA extraction, each specimen
141 was ground with one steel ball (\varnothing 4 mm) and equal amounts of acid washed sand in a 2 ml eppendorf
142 tube at 1500 \times strikes for 180 seconds using a Geno/Grinder 2010 (SPEX SamplePrep, USA). The
143 powdered material was suspended in 300 μl lysis buffer PN and 1 μl RNaseA (100 mg/ml) from the
144 Sbeadex® Mini Plant Kit (LGC Genomics, Germany). The lysate was incubated at 65°C for 30 min
145 followed by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 10 min. Fifty μl of the supernatant was used for DNA
146 extraction, automated with a KingFisher™ Magnetic Particle Processor (Thermo Fisher Scientific,
147 USA) according to manufacturer instructions for the Sbeadex® Mini Plant Kit (LGC Genomics,
148 Germany). DNA was eluted in 50 μl of elution buffer provided by the manufacturer.

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151 2.3 SSR genotyping

152 Seventeen Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) primer pairs previously applied by Stoxen (2012), Jin et al.
153 (2009) and Zhong et al. (2009), were used for molecular genotyping (Table S1). Forward primers were
154 fluorescently 5'-labeled and synthesized by Thermo Fisher Scientific. Reverse primers were
155 synthesized by Eurofins Genomics. SSR loci were amplified in two multiplex PCR reactions using the
156 Type-it microsatellite PCR kit (QIAGEN) in a total volume of 11 µl containing 1.10 µl primer mix
157 (2.0 µM of each primer), 1.10 µl Q-solution, 5.50 µl Type-it Multiplex PCR Master Mix, 2.30 µl
158 Nuclease-Free H₂O and 1 µl of undiluted DNA. The PCR was run at 95 °C for 5 min followed by 12
159 cycles at 95°C for 30 s, 63°C (-0.5°C per cycle) for 90 s and 72°C for 30 s, followed by 23 cycles at
160 95°C for 30 s, 57°C for 90 s and 72 °C for 30 s and a final extension step at 72°C for 10 min. The PCR
161 program was run on Applied Biosystems™2720 Thermal Cycler (Thermo Fisher Scientific). PCR
162 reactions were diluted 1:200 in Nuclease-Free H₂O before size fractionation on Applied Biosystems™
163 3730 DNA analyzer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) using the service at *KIGene*, Karolinska University
164 Hospital, Stockholm, Sweden. The amplicons were visualized in GeneMarker® (Softgenetics) and
165 allele sizes (Table S1, Table S2) were manually scored using the GeneScan™ 600 Liz ® Size Standard
166 (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

167 2.4 Race identification

168 A subset of live bulk samples were selected according to year, country, location, host origin and SSR
169 genotype for race identification using a core set of 20 North American stem rust differential lines
170 according to Jin et al. (2008). Four seedlings of each differential line were sown in pots with a 1:1
171 Pindstrup Substrate peat mix containing slow-release plant nutrients (Pindstrup Mosebrug A/S,
172 Ryomgaard Denmark). The plants were grown in spore-proof cabins in the greenhouse at 17°C during
173 day/12°C during night until full development of first leaf and second leaf half unfolded (approx. 11
174 days after sowing). Spore samples from cold storage were heat-shocked at 43°C for 5 min. Inoculation
175 seedlings was done by spraying 4-5 mg of suspended urediniospores in 5 mL engineered fluid 3M™
176 Novoc™ 7100, (3M, St. Paul, MN, USA) using an airbrush spray gun (standard class, Revell GmbH,
177 Bünde, Germany) in a biosafety cabinet, followed by mist water to ensure dew formation. Seedlings
178 were incubated in a dew chamber at 18°C in darkness for 24 h, then transferred to spore-proof cabins
179 in the quarantine greenhouse with a 16 h photoperiod of natural light and supplemental sodium light
180 (200 µmol s⁻¹ m⁻²), temperature of 20-22°C day/18-20°C night and RH of 80-90%.

181 Seedling infection types (IT) were scored on the first and second leaf 17 days post inoculation using a
182 0-4 scale (Stakman et al., 1962; McIntosh et al., 1995). Isolates conferring ‘low’ ITs, i.e., 0, 0+, 1, 1+,
183 2, and 2+, or combinations thereof, were considered ‘avirulent’ (incompatible), whereas ITs of 3-, 3,
184 3+, and 4 were considered ‘high’ (i.e., compatible, ‘virulent’) (Table S3). In case of distinct different
185 ITs on individual differential lines, which could indicate the presence of more than a single race, one
186 to three single pustules were re-isolated. This procedure was repeated until no further signs of mixed
187 ITs was observed in subsequent race assays. Subsets of isolates representing prevalent clades and races,
188 and four unique races from Spain were tested on 35 additional lines representing diverse sources of
189 stem rust resistance (Table S4). The seeds were supplied by Cereal Disease Laboratory, USDA, and
190 Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC) and multiplied at GRRC; sporadic morphological off-type
191 plants were discarded prior to subsequent seed multiplication. The race typing was generally repeated
192 two to three times, and race nomenclature was based on a modified letter code (Roelfs and Martens,
193 1984) proposed by Jin et al. (2008). Morocco and McNair were used as susceptible controls in all
194 experiments.

195 **2.5 Impact of races on wheat susceptibility**

196 A set of 53-55 European wheat varieties from 18 breeding companies in 12 countries were evaluated
197 for reaction to seven *Pgt* races representing different genetic groups: Clade III-B (TTRTF, IT76c-18),
198 Clade IV-B (TKTTF, ES34-20), Clade IV-F (TKKTF, DK221a-19), Clade I (TTKSK, KE305c-17 and
199 TTKTT, KE181a-18), Clade VIII (RFCNC, CZ59-20), and an unnamed clade (SKGGBR, ES178b2-19).
200 Six seedlings per accession were inoculated under the experimental conditions and procedures
201 described above for race identification. Infection types were scored on the first and second leaf 17 days
202 post inoculation using the 0-4 scale, where host lines with IT responses below 2+ were considered
203 ‘resistant’, ITs 2+ and 3- were considered ‘intermediate’ and lines with ITs of 3 and above were
204 considered ‘susceptible’. Wheat cultivars Morocco and McNair were used as susceptible control (Table
205 S5).

206 **2.6 Compilation of dataset**

207 Duplicate single pustule isolates derived from a bulk sample were removed from the dataset, except
208 when the results revealed multiple genotypes or races within the original sample. Samples that failed
209 recovery were genotyped in case of none or very few samples were recovered from a certain location
210 and year. Alignment with previous international studies based on SNP genotyping was ensured by
211 additional isolates representing already defined genetic groups (Table 2).

212 2.7 Population genetic analyses

213 Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) marker results were investigated through a series of population genetic
 214 analyses. The reliability of SSR markers describing the population structure was assessed through the
 215 detection of multilocus genotypes (MLGs) plotted against the number of loci using the “*poppr*”
 216 package version 2.9.3 implemented in the R environment (Kamvar et al., 2014; Kamvar et al., 2015).
 217 Expected and observed heterozygosity, standard error (SE) of these and inbreeding coefficients ($F_{IS} =$
 218 $(\text{Mean } H_e - \text{Mean } H_o) / \text{Mean } H_e$) were calculated in GenAlEx 6.5 (Peakall and Smouse, 2012). The
 219 genetic diversity within genetic groups as well as within populations was assessed by the number of
 220 MLGs detected within each group using the “*poppr*” package version 2.9.3 implemented in the R
 221 environment (Kamvar et al., 2014; Kamvar et al., 2015). The Shannon-Wiener index (H) was used to
 222 measure genotypic diversity (Shannon, 2001). The standardized index of association (r_{barD}) among
 223 SSR loci with 1000 permutations were calculated to test for association among SSR loci and infer the
 224 mode of reproduction of the different populations (Agapow and Burt, 2001). To avoid the effect of
 225 epidemic clonality, calculations were repeated using clone-corrected datasets, in which only one
 226 representative of each repeated MLG was considered.

227 The population structure of isolates of different geographical origin was investigated by Discriminant
 228 Analysis of Principal Components (DAPC), a multivariate method implemented in the “*adegenet*” R
 229 package version 2.1.5 (Jombart, 2008; Jombart et al., 2010). The *find.clusters* function was used to
 230 determine the *de novo* optimal number of clusters (K), which is normally associated with the lowest
 231 value in the ‘elbow’ of the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) curve. A cross-validation function
 232 (*xvalDapc*) with 1000 replicates, associated with the lowest root mean square error, was used to define
 233 the optimal number of principal components (PCs) to be retained in the DAPC analysis. Membership
 234 probabilities of individual isolates associated to a specific MLG and genetic cluster were calculated
 235 using the “*adegenet*” R package. The relationship of isolates of different MLGs, including reference
 236 isolates representing previously defined genetic groups (Table 2), was calculated using Bruvo distance
 237 and visualized in an unrooted Neighbour Joining tree using 2000 bootstraps in the “*poppr*” R package
 238 using a cut-off value of 75%.

239 3 Results

240 The spatial and temporal distribution of samples of wheat stem rust in this study reflected the large
 241 differences in disease prevalence across countries and years, but with a clear trend of increasing
 242 incidence of stem rust on wheat in Europe since 2016 (Fig. 1, Table 1). Relatively high sampling

243 intensity was made during epidemic situations in southern Italy and western Siberia (Russia), and from
244 non-epidemic situations in most other areas with few and sporadic local outbreaks. Samples from Spain
245 represented two contrasting ecological zones, i.e., areas with nearby plants of alternate hosts of
246 *Berberis spp.*, and other areas distant from such plants. In this study, stem rust was not detected in
247 France until 2019 (one sample from a single location), which increased to 40 samples from 28 locations
248 in 2021. Eleven isolates from the outbreak in Germany (2013), Denmark (2013) and Sweden (2014)
249 and six isolates from a local study in Sweden by Berlin et al. (in prep.) were included as references to
250 earlier and ongoing national studies.

251

252 More than 80% of the samples considered were successfully recovered (cf. Table 1), which provided
253 a unique opportunity to connect information about genetic variability in SSR genotype and virulence
254 phenotype, the latter subjected to strong host-induced selection across very different ecological
255 environments. A total of 540 isolates (2016-2021) were successfully genotyped, of which 81
256 represented duplicate isolates of identical genotypes/races derived from individual bulk samples.
257 Additionally, 46 samples showed signs of more than a single genotype per sample, mainly from areas
258 with high pathogen diversity. None of the 81 duplicate isolates were considered in the study, leaving a
259 total of 459 isolates for onwards analyses. Three genotypes detected in the outbreaks of stem rust in
260 Europe 2013-2014 were resampled, i.e., Clade IV-E.1, Clade IV-E.2, and Clade VIII.

261

262 The majority of the isolates were assigned to four distinct and previously defined clades, which were
263 often present in multiple countries (Fig. 2). Isolates of Clade III-B were the most common, containing
264 one prevalent MLG and a single race known as the ‘Sicily race’ (TTRTF) (Table 3). In 2017 and later
265 years, race TTRTF was also detected in mainland Italy and Sardinia, Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic,
266 Slovak Republic, Slovenia, and Spain. Race TTRTF has virulence to *Sr13b*, of particular relevance for
267 durum wheat, and *Sr35*, *Sr37* and *Sr50* (Table S4). Clade IV-F was detected in 13 countries, but so far
268 not associated with epidemics in Europe outside Italy. Race TKKTF, was also observed in two closely
269 related genetic groups, Clade IV-E.1 (Sweden, Poland) and in Clade IV-E.2 (Italy, Poland, and
270 Sweden). Clade IV-B containing race (TKTTF) was detected in five countries, including France (2020)
271 and Ireland (2020), countries where stem rust is rarely observed. Clade I (Ug99 race group) was not
272 detected in this study. The results confirm the spreading of relatively few clones across multiple
273 countries in northern and western Europe in recent years, giving rise to sporadic incidences of stem

274 rust on wheat in some countries, and more systematic and widespread occurrence in other cases, e.g.,
 275 in France, 2021.

276 Multiple genetic groups, which have not been named previously, were termed ‘Others’ (Fig. 2, Table
 277 3). These groups were prevalent in local areas in Sweden, Spain, and Russia, often sampled from
 278 cereals in proximity to the alternate host, *Berberis* spp. Many of the races were characterized by
 279 avirulence on multiple wheat differential lines (Supplementary Tables S3 and S4) and some of the
 280 isolates revealed unexpected, intermediate infection types. In summary, the results suggested the
 281 presence of local highly diverse *Pgt* populations in Russia, Spain and Sweden consisting of multiple
 282 races, and in most other areas, clonal populations consisting of only few genetic groups and races.

283 3.1 Genetic diversity

284 The genetic structure of *Pgt* was investigated for seven geographically and ecologically different
 285 sampling areas (populations), i.e., Italy, Spain (Barberry area), Spain (non-Barberry area), Sweden,
 286 Russia (Siberia), France and Europe (other). The latter represents 11 countries, where wheat stem rust
 287 was observed only sporadically, resulting in relatively few samples compared to a large geographical
 288 sampling area (Table 4).

289

290 The 17 SSR primers revealed a total of 104 multilocus genotypes (MLGs) based on a total of 179
 291 different alleles (Table 4, Fig. S1). The seven populations revealed very different degree of genetic
 292 diversity. The populations in Italy, Spain (non-barberry area) and France had low number of genotypes
 293 compared to sampling size, low Shannon-Weiner diversity index, high level of linkage disequilibrium
 294 (Table 4) and excess of observed heterozygosity as compared to the expected under Hardy–Weinberg
 295 (HW) equilibrium (Fig. 3). These features are strong signatures of clonal reproduction. In contrast, the
 296 populations from Spain (barberry area), Sweden and Russia showed strong signatures of sexual
 297 reproduction, revealed by high numbers of genotypes compared to sampling size, high diversity
 298 indexes and linkage disequilibria close to zero in Russia and slightly higher in Spain (barberry area)
 299 and Sweden. Observed/expected heterozygosity were in HW proportions for Russia or lower than
 300 expected for Spain (barberry) and Sweden, which may indicate some degree of inbreeding in the last
 301 two mentioned. This is in line with F_{IS} values of 0.14 and 0.25, respectively for these two populations
 302 as opposed to 0.019 for Russia and negative values for the clonal populations in Italy, France and Spain
 303 (non-barberry) (Fig. 3). Samples from Europe (other), representing sporadic sampling in many
 304 countries across several years, had parameter values between these extremes, which suggests that

305 regions in Europe, where stem rust is not yet established, may be influenced by incursions of
 306 individuals of diverse evolutionary origin.

307 The DAPC analysis revealed five genetic clusters based on 20 retained PCs and six discriminant (DA)
 308 eigenvalues, which were sufficient to capture the genetic structure of the whole dataset (Fig. 4, Fig.
 309 S2). This corresponded with the optimal value of BIC indicated by the lowest value of the elbow
 310 observed in the BIC curve (Fig. S3). The 104 MLGs detected among the 459 isolates included in the
 311 study were clustered in the DAPC analyses based on membership probabilities larger than 0.9999
 312 (Table S6). Cluster 1 consisted of previously defined clades, such as Clade IV-A.1, Clade IV-B, Clade
 313 IV-F, Clade IV-E.1, and Clade IV-E.2. Cluster 4 consisted of five closely related MLGs in Clade III-
 314 B. Both clusters (CL1 and CL4), consisting of previously defined groups, were clearly separated from
 315 the three others. Cluster 5 consisted of a diverse population from Russia (western Siberia) and Clade
 316 VIII consisting of only two MLGs mainly detected in eastern Europe. Cluster 2 consisted of MLGs
 317 representing isolates from Sweden, a single MLG detected in Norway, a different MLG detected in
 318 Czech Republic and a re-sampled MLG detected in Denmark. Finally, Cluster 3 consisted of 28 MLGs
 319 from Spain and 8 MLGs from Sweden.

320 The overall conclusions from the DAPC analyses were confirmed by phylogenetic analyses (Fig. 5),
 321 which also comprised reference isolates representing genetic groups reported in previous European and
 322 international studies (cf. Table 2). **One branch** consisted of already defined clades, most of which
 323 have been previously detected in Europe, i.e., clade IV-A.1, IV-A.2, IV-E.1, IV-E.2, and IV-F
 324 (equivalent to CL1, Fig. 4). Clade III-B formed a unique group of five closely related MLGs, equivalent
 325 to CL4 in Fig. 4. A **second branch** consisted of 38 diverse MLGs from two local areas near Omsk and
 326 Novosibirsk in western Siberia, Russia, which corresponded with CL5 in Fig. 4. A Clade III-A
 327 reference isolate and an isolate from the German outbreak in 2013 (unpublished) were part of CL5.
 328 Whereas the two MLGs in the newly defined Clade VIII grouped with the Russian isolates in the DAPC
 329 analysis, this was not the case in the NJ tree, where they were located within a **third branch** consisting
 330 of genetically diverse isolates from Scandinavia and Czech Republic (CL2 in Fig. 4). A **fourth branch**
 331 consisted of 36 MLGs representing isolates from Spain and Sweden, corresponding to CL3 (Fig. 4).

332 In conclusion, the local sexual populations in Spain (barberry area), Sweden and Russia, respectively,
 333 were highly diverse and formed distinct genetic groups. These were clearly separated from previously
 334 named and prevalent clades, each consisting of one or few races and/or MLGs. One MLG from Clade
 335 VIII, which was already detected in the German outbreak in 2013, was resampled in Czech Republic,
 336 Slovakia and Hungary in the present study, and in another case, an MLG first detected in a sexual

337 population in Sweden (2019) was detected in Denmark (2020). Other reference isolates, e.g., Clade I
 338 (Ug99), Clade II, Clade III-A, Clade IV-C and Clade IV-D, were not detected in this study.

339 **3.2 Diversity by virulence in local populations in Spain, Sweden, and Russia**

340 In addition to typical races found in Europe, samples from barberry areas in Spain, Sweden, and Russia
 341 revealed a high number of unique races in low frequencies and unusual virulence combinations, and
 342 occasional unexpected infection types (IT) on specific combinations of differential lines (Table S3,
 343 S4).

344 In Spain, 54 of 58 genotyped isolates were successfully virulence phenotyped based on the IT responses
 345 on 20 wheat lines collectively assembled to differentiate races in *Pgt* (Table 5). The results were highly
 346 dependent on sampling area, i.e., high race diversity in areas in proximity of alternate hosts of *Berberis*
 347 spp. (28 races among 30 isolates), and low diversity in areas where the alternate host was not detected
 348 near sampling sites (4 races among 24 isolates). In general, different races were represented by different
 349 genotypes (MLGs). Only in four cases, different races shared the same genotype, i.e., races within
 350 MLG ID number 6, 11, 23 and 89, respectively (Table 5).

351

352 The presence of *Sr31*-virulence in 22 races was striking, irrespective of host origin, representing wheat,
 353 rye, and a wild grass (*Elymus repens*). A subset of four of these isolates were tested on 35 additional
 354 wheat lines representing diverse and occasionally newly identified sources of resistance (Table S4).
 355 These results confirmed highly unusual and different virulence patterns, e.g., confirming virulence to
 356 *Sr31* using three wheat lines, Federation*4/Kavkaz, Sr31/6*LMPG and Siouxland, as well as virulence
 357 to *Sr22*, *Sr24*, *Sr44*, *Sr45*, *Sr49*, and *Sr50*. In addition, we observed higher than expected ITs for three
 358 incompatible interactions involving *Sr31* (2, 2+ and 22+), *Sr24* (22+), and *Sr50* (2-). The fact that *Sr31*-
 359 virulent races were observed for samples collected from three host genera (*Triticum*, *Secale* and
 360 *Elymus*), and the lack of differentiation according to host origin with respect to virulence/race pattern
 361 in general, demonstrated that wheat adapted stem rust from local areas in Spain were able to infect and
 362 reproduce on rye and wild grasses.

363 In contrast, the samples from agricultural areas separated from alternate hosts, *Berberis* spp., revealed
 364 only four races; TKTTF (from bread wheat, durum wheat and spelt), TKRTF (bread wheat), and
 365 TKKTF and TTRTF, the latter two collected from both bread wheat and durum wheat. The four races
 366 were assigned to three clades that were also detected at multiple locations outside Spain (Fig. 2).

367 Twenty-nine live isolates from Sweden revealed 13 race phenotypes, representing five reference
 368 samples from a local study in Sweden (2017), two collections from barley in 2018 and one collection
 369 from wheat in 2019 and 2020 (Table 6). A single race/genotype (QCHNC; MLG40) was resampled
 370 twice from a single wheat plot in Denmark (2020).

371 TKKTF was detected in two different clades, IV-E.1, and IV-F, but also represented in a reference
 372 isolate from Sweden, 2014 (Clade IV-E.2). Except for TKKTF and TTQKF, the races in Sweden were
 373 characterized by a relatively high number of avirulences. None of the races, except TKKTF and
 374 QCHNC mentioned above, were detected outside Sweden. In contrast to Spain, *Sr24-*, *Sr31-*, and *Sr50-*
 375 virulences were not detected. The unusual virulence patterns and complexity of races confirmed the
 376 high degree of genotypic diversity and separation from other populations in the study.

377

378 Fifty-three live isolates from western Siberia were race phenotyped, representing the majority of
 379 samples from two neighboring regions in 2016 and 2017 that were successfully genotyped (Table 7).
 380 A total of 35 races were detected, of which only five were found more than once. All races were
 381 different from races detected elsewhere in the study, which was confirmed by the fact that none of
 382 previously defined clades in Europe, Africa, Asia and North America were detected (Table 7). In
 383 general, different races were represented by different genotypes, except MLG 100, which was
 384 represented by four races (LCCSF, LCRSF, QCHSF, and QCRSF). Interestingly, a single race has
 385 *Sr31*-virulence (race profile no. 8), but is indeed very different from known races of Ug99 and *Sr31*-
 386 virulent races from Spain (this study). The *Sr31*-virulence was confirmed by repeated tests using *Sr31*
 387 resistance in three genetic backgrounds. Overall, the races had ~~very~~ different virulence/avirulence
 388 pattern ranging from individuals with relatively few virulences, e.g., race profile 1 (virulences:
 389 5,9g,17,9a,9d,10,38) to individuals with high number of virulences, e.g., race profile 35 (virulences:
 390 5,21,9e,7b,6,8a,9g,36,9b,17,9a,10,38, Tmp).

391 **3.3 Impact of races on wheat susceptibility**

392 Seedling tests using seven isolates representing different genetic groups (Fig. 5) demonstrated that
 393 most of the investigated wheat varieties were susceptible to most of the races (Table 8). The two Ug99
 394 races revealed susceptibility to the highest number of varieties, whereas the race SKGBR from a
 395 recombining population in Spain was less adapted to the varieties investigated. Information about the
 396 detailed responses of individual varieties to individual races are provided in Table S5.

397 **4 Discussion**

398 The present study represents a comprehensive dataset based on SSR genotyping and race phenotyping
399 of more than 400 samples of *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici*, which were collected in 17 European
400 countries and Siberia between 2016 and 2021. By comparing to results of isolates of non-European
401 origin, hosted by the GRRC (www.wheatrust.org), and reference isolates from the USDA ARS Cereal
402 Disease Lab, we were able to address hypotheses about possible origin and spatial patterns of the re-
403 emergence of wheat stem rust in Europe since the outbreak in Sicily in 2016 (Bhattacharya, 2017).
404 Sampling in local areas in proximity to the alternate host, *Berberis* spp., and in corresponding non-
405 *Berberis* areas, allowed us to investigate the current role of *Berberis* spp. in wheat stem rust
406 epidemiology in Europe. This is a question, which has occupied scientists and plant breeders
407 historically, e.g., Stakman (1923), Hermansen (1968), Lind (1915), and in recent years the discussion
408 about the potential role of common barberry has been brought up again due to the repeal of *Berberis*
409 eradication laws in several European countries in the 1990s (Berlin et al., 2012) and the replanting of
410 rust susceptible *Berberis* spp. for environmental purposes, e.g., in the United Kingdom (Saunders et
411 al., 2019). The conclusions in this study were supported by different population genetic and plant
412 pathology approaches, which generally resulted in similar outcomes.

413 Since the local outbreaks in Germany in 2013 (Olivera Firpo et al., 2017), Sicily in 2016 (Patpour et
414 al., 2020), Sweden in 2017 (Berlin, 2017) and Siberia in 2016-2017 (Shamanin et al., 2020), stem rust
415 has been increasingly frequent in northern and western Europe, e.g., in France (2021), where it has
416 been reported only sporadically since the 1970s (Massenot, 1978). This is consistent with aerial spread
417 of urediniospores across large distances, giving rise to observations of stem rust on wheat in new areas
418 in Europe. The detection of relatively few clonal lineages (genotypes) of particular races, some of
419 which have been detected outside Europe in previous years, e.g., Olivera et al. (2019);
420 www.wheatrust.org, underline the capacity of well-adapted *Pgt* races to reproduce clonally and spread
421 across large areas within relatively few years (Hermansen, 1968; Brown and Hovmøller, 2002;
422 Hovmøller et al., 2016; Walter et al., 2016).

423 It may be difficult to establish the exact geographical or evolutionary origin of newly emerged
424 genotypes/races of airborne plant pathogens due to lack of regular and extensive population surveys.
425 In this study, we used a combination of molecular genotype and race phenotype assays, which were
426 designed for resolving long-term genetic relationships using selective neutral markers, and short-term
427 responses to host induced selection governed by R-genes in host plants, respectively. We observed

428 evidence of resampling of some of the genotypes/races, which have been detected previously in
429 Europe, e.g., in the local outbreaks in Germany (2013): Clade VIII (RFCNC), Clade IV-E.1 (TKKTF),
430 and Clade IV-E.2 (TKKTF). Clade VIII was resampled several times in Czech Republic and Slovakia
431 (race RFCNC) and in Hungary (race RFCPC). Otherwise, Clade VIII has been reported in a single
432 isolate (race RSBNC) from Italy in 1985 (Szabo et al., 2022).

433 Clade III-B consists of a single race (TTRTF) and five closely related MLGs. The most prevalent of
434 these MLGs were detected in the Sicily outbreak in 2016, which may designate the return of stem rust
435 in Europe at epidemic levels (Bhattacharya, 2017). The same MLG and race was prevalent in Eritrea
436 in East Africa in the same year (Patpour et al., 2020). However, the first observation dates back to 2014
437 in Georgia, where it was sampled at low frequency in a genetically diverse population (Olivera et al.,
438 2019). Clade IV-F, which in this study contained a single race (TKKTF), was first detected in 2018 in
439 Italy, Sweden, and Poland. Clade IV-F was first detected in the southern Caucasus region, i.e., sampled
440 in 2014 in Georgia (Olivera et al., 2019) and in 2015 and 2016 in Azerbaijan, Iraq and Eritrea (GRRC;
441 www.wheatrust.org). Clade IV-B, which in this study was first detected in Croatia (2017), has been
442 widespread in multiple countries in East Africa and the Middle East in years before 2016 (GRRC;
443 www.wheatrust.org). In Europe, Clade IV-B consists solely of race TKTTF, but in East Africa also of
444 race TTTTF (GRRC; [wheatrust.org](http://www.wheatrust.org)), suggesting a close relationship between these races. Similar
445 patterns have been observed for more than 10 different races in the Ug99 race group in East Africa,
446 which all belong to Clade I (Singh et al., 2016). On the other hand, a single race, TKTTF, was detected
447 in three distinct genetic groups. In East Africa, TKTTF, also known as the ‘Digalu’ race, was assigned
448 Clade IV-A.1 and Clade IV-B (Olivera et al., 2015), and in the German outbreak in 2013, TKTTF were
449 represented in both Clade-A.1 and Clade-A.2 (Olivera Firpo et al., 2017). This may suggest
450 independent evolution of virulence in these genetic groups, stressing that a combination of molecular
451 genotype and race phenotype assays are crucial to resolve the population biology of biotrophic plant
452 pathogens such as *Pgt*, where disease prevention is often governed by R-genes in the host plant.

453 In contrast to the clonal population structure in most areas investigated in this study, high levels of
454 diversity with respect to SSR and virulence were detected in local areas in Spain, Sweden and western
455 Siberia where alternate hosts for yellow- and stem rust, *Berberis vulgaris* and/or indigenous subspecies
456 are present (Rodriguez-Algaba et al., 2021). The indicators of sexual reproduction in these local areas
457 were among others, *i*) high numbers of MLGs and races relative to sample sizes, *ii*) high diversity
458 indexes, *iii*) low index of association (almost random association in several cases), and *iv*) deficit or
459 proportional levels of heterozygosity compared to expected under HW equilibrium. For the Spanish

460 (barberry) and Swedish populations, the observed heterozygosity was lower than the expected
461 indicating some degree of inbreeding in these local, diverse populations in proximity to the alternate
462 host.

463 Several of the same features have been observed in sexually reproduced populations of *P. striiformis*
464 in the Himalayan region of Asia, e.g., (Ali et al., 2014; Hovmøller et al., 2016; Thach et al., 2016), oat
465 and rye stem rust populations in Sweden (Berlin et al., 2012), wheat stem rust in Georgia (Olivera et
466 al., 2019), and with respect to race distribution in local populations of wheat stem rust in the USA
467 (Groth and Roelfs, 1982). The features above are strong indicators of *Berberis* spp. as an important
468 component in the epidemiology of wheat stem rust in Europe, although unique genotypes/races from
469 local populations in Sweden/Spain were rarely observed in distant areas. We observed a unique MLG
470 and race in Denmark in 2020 that was first detected in a local sexual population in Sweden in 2019,
471 and a unique genotype sampled in Norway in 2021 was also part of the sexual population in Sweden.
472 Overall, our observations suggest that stem rust is persistent in Europe from one year to the next, and
473 more intensive sampling efforts would most likely reveal additional cases of resampling of genotypes
474 derived from sexual reproduction on *Berberis* spp. in Europe.

475 The study revealed highly interesting features with respect to race and virulence in the European
476 population. It was striking that in most cases, only a single race was detected within an individual
477 MLG, occasionally two races only differentiated by a single virulence character. The SSR genotyping
478 therefore to a large extent reflects the presence of individual races, which represents a cheap and rapid
479 complementary tool for time consuming and costly race assays. However, in a longer time and area
480 perspective, additional virulences may emerge within existing genotypes, in stem rust most evident by
481 the evolution of 15 races within the Ug99 genetic lineage, e.g., Singh et al. (2011), Patpour et al. (2015);
482 [RustTracker website](#)), and in wheat yellow rust there are multiple examples, e.g., Wellings and
483 McIntosh (1990), Hovmøller et al. (2011), and Thach et al. (2016), www.wheatrust.org. The latter
484 feature stresses the importance of a continuous search for additional genotyping markers and
485 procedures in pathogen surveillance programs to keep pace with the ongoing evolution of new races.

486 *Sr31*-virulence was observed in multiple and highly diverse races in local populations in Spain, and a
487 single case in a population from Siberia. None of these were related to Ug99, demonstrating that *Sr31*-
488 virulence is not unique to Ug99 (Pretorius et al., 2000), which has been the general conception since
489 the emergence of this historical race in East Africa in 1999 (Olivera et al., 2022). The latter study
490 reported a single isolate carrying virulence to *Sr31* collected in 2018 in one of the local barberry areas
491 in Spain, in proximity to the ones represented in our study. Twenty-two of the 28 recovered races from

492 these areas carried *Sr31*-virulence in our study, irrespective of cereal/grass host origin, i.e., bread
493 wheat, rye and a grass weed, *Elymus* spp. All isolates of these diverse races were successfully recovered
494 and tested on wheat differential lines, which demonstrate that wheat adapted stem rust may also grow
495 on rye, barley and wild grasses. These observations call for additional studies about existing and
496 potential break-down of the host barriers that have been used to define *formae speciales* within *P.*
497 *graminis* (Anikster, 1985). The presence of a *Sr31*-virulent race in an independent Siberian population
498 stress that virulence may emerge independently and multiple times when large geographical areas and
499 time spans are considered.

500 The present study was facilitated by long-term commitments of collaborators from leading rust
501 diagnostic laboratories in Europe, USA and Russia. Particular efforts were made to ensure alignment
502 of results between genotyping platforms based on SNP and SSR procedures, and virulence phenotyping
503 using the same core set of wheat lines differentiating races of stem rust. This was done by exchanging
504 isolates (under quarantine conditions) and DNA samples representing all previously defined
505 clades/genetic groups in *Pgt* between the Cereal Disease Lab (Minnesota, USA) and GRRC
506 (Denmark), which were tested in duplicates using SNP and SSR genotyping in parallel. In this way, it
507 was possible to establish a strong link between the current dataset based on SSR procedures and
508 previous international studies based on SNP procedures, e.g., Olivera et al. (2015), Olivera Firpo et al.
509 (2017), Olivera et al. (2019).

510 The alignment efforts presented in this study may represent a major step forward in our efforts to
511 strengthen coordinated rust surveillance for international research projects and global early warning
512 systems for not only stem rust, but also yellow rust and leaf rust infecting wheat. Alignment and
513 common standards for experimentation and exchange of data and results has made it possible to present
514 new results from multiple laboratories in a global context, as demonstrated by the Wheat Rust Toolbox
515 (www.wheatrust.org) hosted by GRRC and associated websites for everyone interested. The burning
516 question in years ahead is to which extent it will be possible to sustain the attention of both public and
517 private donors to further develop even more timely and accurate early warning for disease outbreaks
518 in major agricultural crops in Europe and beyond.

519 **Conflict of Interest**

520 *The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial*
521 *relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.*

522

523 **Author contributions**

524 MH, MP, JRA and AJ designed the study and wrote the manuscript; MP recovered and multiplied live
525 isolates and performed the race phenotyping; JRA, TT and AJ performed the genotyping and data
526 analyses, LZ performed the SNP genotyping of reference isolates at CDL; AB, YJ, DV designed
527 sampling strategy and facilitated sampling in barberry areas in Sweden and Spain, respectively; VP
528 and ES designed sampling strategy and facilitated sampling in western Siberia; BR, KF, PC, AH, SS,
529 KM and RV facilitated sampling in Italy, Germany, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia and France,
530 respectively, and ensured alignment with race phenotyping results in the national rust surveillance
531 programs in these countries; JH uploaded genotyping and phenotyping data to the Wheat Rust Toolbox,
532 and developed the graphical presentation of results on maps. All authors read, contributed to the
533 revision, and accepted the manuscript.

534

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545

546

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556

557 **Data Availability Statement**

558 The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/supplementary material.
 559 The SSR genotypic data of the 459 isolates included in the present study are available at
 560 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6227898>.

561

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684

685 **Figure 1.** Sampling sites in Europe 2016-2021. Each dot represents a sampling site where one or more
686 samples were collected for genotype/race analyses. Additional sampling sites near Omsk and
687 Novosibirsk in western Siberia not shown.

688

689 **Figure 2.** Frequency distribution of genetic groups among 459 isolates of *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici*
690 in Europe between 2016 and 2021. The designation of distinct groups follow the nomenclature

691 suggested by Szabo et al. (2022)2022). ‘Others’ refer to genetic groups, which have not yet been named
 692 internationally. Downloaded 3rd February 2022.

693

694 **Figure 3.** Observed heterozygosity (H_o), expected heterozygosity (H_e) and inbreeding coefficients
 695 (F_{is}) of geographical spaced populations of *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici* in Europe and Siberia.
 696 Samples from outside these areas were not considered due to low sample sizes in individual countries.
 697 Vertical bars represent standard errors (SE), level of significance: $P < 0.001$ ***, $P < 0.01$ **, $P < 0.05$ *.

698

699 **Figure 4.** Discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) for the 104 multilocus genotypes
 700 (MLGs) detected (clone corrected data). The axes represent the first two linear discriminants. Each
 701 ellipsis represents distinct genetic clusters and dots represent individuals associated with unique MLGs.
 702 Eigenvalues indicate the amount of genetic information retained by the PCA (left inset) and the
 703 discriminant function (DA, right inset).

704

705 **Figure 5.** Unrooted Neighbor Joining tree (clone-corrected data) using Bruvo’s distance showing the
 706 genetic relationship of European stem rust isolates (2016-2021) and additional reference isolates
 707 representing previously defined genetic groups (Clades) detected in Europe and elsewhere. National
 708 letter codes are indicative: ES (Spain), SE (Sweden), RU (Russia). Red dots represent isolates used for
 709 assessment of host susceptibility.

710

711 **Table 1.** Number of dead and recovered stem rust samples collected between 2016 and 2021.

Country	Sampling year	Sample status		
		Dead	Recovered	Total
Austria	2020, 2021	0	5	5
Belgium	2021	1	1	2
Croatia	2017	9	2	11
Czech Republic	2018, 2020, 2021	1	11	12
Denmark	2018-2021	2	15	17
France	2019, 2020, 2021	14	28	42
Germany	2019, 2020	0	4	4
Hungary	2019, 2020	1	2	3
Ireland	2020	1	1	2

Italy	2016-2021	35	166	201
Norway	2020, 2021	0	3	3
Poland	2019, 2020	1	8	9
Russia	2016, 2017	6	38	44
Slovak Republic	2018, 2020, 2021	2	18	20
Slovenia	2020, 2021	5	9	14
Spain	2018-2021	3	34	37
Sweden	2017-2019, 2021	10	33	43
Switzerland	2021	0	10	10
Total		91	388	479

712

713 **Table 2.** Reference isolates of diverse origin, including isolates from the outbreak in Germany in 2013
714 to facilitate alignment of race, SSR genotype and SNP genotype in *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici*.

Genetic group/Clade	Ref isolate	Provided by ^a	Geographical origin	Genotyping method	Reference	Confirmed race
Clade I	07KEN24-4	CDL	East Africa	SNP chip & SSR	Szabo et al. 2022	TTTSK
Clade I	ET165-12	GRRC	East Africa	SNP chip & SSR	Current paper	TTKSK
Clade II	13ETH25-2	CDL	East Africa	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2015	JRCQC
Clade II	ET45a1-14	GRRC	East Africa	SNP chip & SSR	Current paper	JRCQC
Clade III-A	06YEM34-1	CDL	Middle East	SNP chip & SSR	Szabo et al. 2022	TRTTF
Clade III-B	14GEO189-1	CDL	West Asia	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2019	TTRTF
Clade III-B	IT14a1-16	GRRC	Europe	SNP core set & SSR	Current paper	TTRTF
Clade IV-A.1	13GER17-3	CDL	Germany (2013)	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2017	-
Clade IV-A.1	DE205a-13	GRRC	Germany (2013)	SNP chip & SSR	Current paper	TKTTF
Clade IV-A.2	13GER10-4	CDL	Germany (2013)	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2017, Szabo et al. 2022	TKTTF
Clade IV-A.2	DK185a-13	GRRC	Europe	SNP chip & SSR	Current paper	TKTTF
Clade IV-B	TZ92a-16	GRRC	East Africa	SNP core set & SSR	Current paper	TTTTF
Clade IV-B	ET320a-15	GRRC	East Africa	SNP chip & SSR	Current paper	TKTTF
Clade IV-C	13GER06-1	CDL	Germany (2013)	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2017, Szabo et al. 2022	PKPTF
Clade IV-C	AZ180a-14	GRRC	West Asia	SNP chip & SSR	Current paper	PKTTF
Clade IV-D	13GER01-1	CDL	Germany (2013)	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2017, Szabo et al. 2022	TKKTF
Clade IV-E.1	13GER16-4	CDL	Germany (2013)	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2017, Szabo et al. 2022	TKKTP
Clade IV-E.1	DEWST62-13-10	GRRC	Germany (2013)	SSR	Current paper	TKKTP

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Clade IV-E.2	13GER08-1	CDL	Germany (2013)	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2017	-
Clade IV-E.2	SE373a1-14	GRRRC	Europe	SNP chip & SSR	Current paper	TKKTF
Clade IV-F	14GEO190-2	CDL	West Asia	SNP chip & SSR	Olivera et al. 2019, Szabo et al. 2022	TKFTF
Clade IV-F	IT33a-18	GRRRC	Europe	SSR	Current paper	TKKTF
Clade VI-C	75-36-700-3 (SZA7a)	CDL	North America	SNP chip & SSR	Szabo et al. 2022	SCCLC
Clade VIII	WST55-13-6	JKI	Germany (2013)	SSR	Current paper	HFCNC
-	WSR67-13-5	JKI	Germany (2013)	SSR	Current paper	MMMTF

^a USDA-ARS Cereal Disease Laboratory, University of Minnesota, USA, GRRRC: Global Rust Reference Center, Aarhus University, Denmark, JKI: Julius Kühn-Institut, Dresden, Germany.

715

716 **Table 3.** Races detected in Europe within previously defined genetic groups (clades) and number of
 717 MLGs in these. ‘Other’ represents 76 races among 92 MLGs detected in the genetic group; n.a.: not
 718 race typed.

Clade name	Number of MLGs	Race name	Virulence profile	Total
Clade III-B	5	TTRTF	5,21,9e,7b,11,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	56
		n.a.		79
Clade IV-A.1	1	TKTTF	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	1
Clade IV-B	1	TKTTF	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	24
		TKRTF	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	1
		n.a.		30
Clade IV-E.1	1	TKKTF	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	2
Clade IV-E.2	1	TKKTF	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	6
		n.a.		1
Clade IV-F	1	TKKTF	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	36
		n.a.		69
Clade VIII	2	RFCNC	5,21,-,7b,-,-,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,-,10,-,-,-,McN	11
		RFCPC	5,21,-,7a,-,-,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,-,10,Tmp,-,-,-,McN	2
		n.a.		5
Other	92	= 76 races		108
		n.a.		28
Total	104			459

719

720

721 **Table 4.** Genetic diversity of geographical spaced populations of *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici* in
 722 Europe and Russia. Linkage disequilibrium and rbarD based on clone-corrected data.

Geographical population	Number of samples (n)	Number of MLGs	Number of MLG/n	Shannon-Weiner H index	rbarD	
					value	P-value
Italy	150	7	0.047	0.944	0.469	0.001
France	42	2	0.048	0.675	0.983	0.001
Spain non-barberry	26	4	0.154	1.003	0.515	0.001
Spain barberry	32	28	0.875	3.292	0.012	0.044
Sweden	43	25	0.581	2.943	0.087	0.001
Russia	63	40	0.635	3.160	<0.001	0.471
Other (Europe)	103	11	0.075	1.672	0.104	0.002

723

724 **Table 5.** Virulence diversity of 31 races of *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici* in areas in Spain in proximity
 725 of *Berberis* species. and in areas where the alternate host was absent. Shaded cells represent *Sr31*-
 726 virulent races.

Area	Race profile no.	Host	Virulence formula	Race name	SSR name	MLG ID	Total
	1	Bread Wheat	-,21,9e,-,11,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,17,-,-,-,-,31,38,McN	JTHBK	Other	92	1
	2	Elymus repens	-,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,31,38,McN	KKGBK	Other	62	1
	3	Bread Wheat	-,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,24,-,-,McN	KKGBM	Other	12	1
	4	Bread Wheat	-,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,9a,-,-,-,24,-,38,McN	KKGLP	Other	35	1
	5	Bread Wheat	5,-,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,9a,-,-,-,31,-,McN	PKGLH	Other	39	1
	6	Rye	5,-,9e,7b,11,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,31,-,McN	PTGBH	Other	11	1
	7	Rye	5,-,9e,7b,11,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,10,Tmp,-,31,-,McN	PTGFH	Other	11	1
	8	Rye	5,21,-,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,31,38,McN	RKBBK	Other	16	1
	9	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,-,-,-,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-	SCGBB	Other	9	1
	10	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,24,-,38,McN	SKBBP	Other	13	1
	11	Rye	5,21,9e,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,McN	SKGBC	Other	45	1
	12	Elymus repens	5,21,9e,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,38,McN	SKGBF	Other	4	1
	13	Rye	5,21,9e,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,-,31,-,McN	SKGBH	Other	22	1
	14	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,24,31,-,McN	SKGBR	Other	41	1
	15	Rye	5,21,9e,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,24,31,-,McN	SKGBR	Other	89	1
Barberry area	16	Elymus repens	5,21,9e,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,-,24,31,38,McN	SKGBT	Other	15	1
					Other	19	1
	17	Elymus repens	5,21,9e,-,11,6,-,9g,-,9b,-,-,9a,-,-,-,31,-,McN	SRGLH	Other	7	1

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	18	Rye	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,30,-,9a,-,-,-,31,38,McN	TKDLK	Other	6	1
	19	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,31,-,McN	TKGBH	Other	2	1
	20	Rye	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,31,38,McN	TKGBK	Other	5	1
	21	Rye	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,24,31,-,McN	TKGBR	Other	89	1
	22	Rye	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,-,-,10,-,-,31,-,McN	TKGDH	Other	6	1
	23	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,9a,-,-,-,31,-,McN	TKGLH	Other	46	1
	24	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,9a,-,-,-,31,38,McN	TKGLK	Other	10	1
non-Barberry area	25	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,17,-,-,10,-,24,31,-,McN	TKHDR	Other	3	1
					Other	93	1
	26	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,11,-,8a,9g,-,-,-,-,9a,-,-,-,31,-,McN	TPBLH	Other	23	1
	27	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,11,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,-,9a,-,-,-,31,-,-	TTGLG	Other	23	1
	28	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,11,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,17,9a,-,-,-,31,-,McN	TTHLH	Other	99	1
	29	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	TKKTF	Clade IV-F	103	2
		Durum wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN				4
	30	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	TKRTF	Clade IV-B	101	1
	31	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	TKTTF	Clade IV-B	101	12
		Durum wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN				1
Spelt		5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	1				
32	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,11,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN	TTRTF	Clade III-B	28	1	
	Durum wheat	5,21,9e,7b,11,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,38,McN				2	
Total							54

727

728 **Table 6.** Virulence diversity of 13 races of *P. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* in Sweden 2017-2021. Isolates were
729 derived from samples collected from cultivated barley and bread wheat in areas where *Berberis*
730 *vulgaris* was present. Reference samples from Berlin et al. 2021 (unpublished) are marked in bold in
731 the MLG ID column.

Race profile no.	Host	Virulence formula	Race name	SSR name	MLG ID	Total
1	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,-,-,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,-,-,-,-,McN	LFCLC	Other	98	1
2	Barley	5,-,-,-,-,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,-,10,-,-,-,-,McN	LFCNC	Other	8	1
	Bread Wheat			Other	83	1
3	Barley	5,-,-,-,-,8a,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,-,10,-,-,-,-,McN	LFMNC	Other	68	3
4	Barley	5,-,-,7b,-,-,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,-,10,-,-,-,-,McN	MFCNC	Other	61	1
	Bread Wheat				1	1
	Bread Wheat				14	1

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5	Barley	5,-,-,7b,-,-,8a,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,-,10,Tmp,-,-,-,McN	MFMP	Other	68	2
6	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,-,-,-,9g,-,9b,-,17,9a,-,10,-,-,-,McN	QCHNC	Other	40	1
7	Barley	5,21,-,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,17,9a,-,-,-,-,McN	QKHLC	Other	90	3
	Barley			Other	91	2
8	Barley	5,21,-,-,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,-,-,-,-,McN	QKRLC	Other	90	3
9	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,-,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,-,10,Tmp,-,-,-,McN	RCCPC	Other	95	4
10	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,-,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,-,10,Tmp,-,-,-,McN	RFCPC	Other	37	1
11	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,-,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,McN	RFCTC	Other	36	1
12	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	TKKTF	Clade IV-E.1	25	1
	Bread Wheat			Clade IV-F	103	1
13	Barley	5,21,9e,7b,11,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,-,-,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	TTQKF	Other	56	1
Total						29

732

733 **Table 7.** Virulence diversity of 35 races of *P. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* in Russia 2016-2017. Isolates were
 734 derived from samples collected from cultivated barley, bread wheat and durum wheat near Omsk and
 735 Novosibirsk. Shaded cells represent a *Sr31*-virulent race.

736

Race profile no.	Host	Virulence formula	Race name	SSR name	MLG ID	Total
1	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,-,-,-,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	LCCSF	Other	100	3
					50	1
2	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,-,-,-,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	LCRSF	Other	100	4
3	Durum wheat	5,-,-,-,-,-,8a,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	LFMSF	Other	57	1
					55	1
4	Durum wheat	5,-,-,-,-,-,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	LFRSF	Other	60	1
5	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,-,-,6,-,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	LHCSF	Other	70	1
6	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,-,-,6,-,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	LHRSF	Other	66	1
7	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	LKCSF	Other	87	2
					88	1
8	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,-,11,6,8a,9g,-,-,-,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,31,38,McN	LTBSK	Other	21	1
9	Durum wheat	5,-,-,-,11,6,8a,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	LTMSF	Other	63	1
10	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,7b,-,-,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	MCMSF	Other	59	1
11	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,7b,-,-,8a,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,McN	MFMTF	Other	71	1
12	Bread Wheat	5,-,-,7b,11,-,8a,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,McN	MPMTC	Other	64	1
13	Barley	5,-,9e,-,-,-,8a,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	NFMSF	Other	58	1

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	Bread Wheat					1
14	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,-,-,-,9g,-,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	QCHSF	Other	100	4
15	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,-,-,-,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	QCRSF	Other	100	5
16	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,-,-,-,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	QFRSF	Other	42	1
17	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,-,-,6,-,9g,-,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,McN	QHHSC	Other	49	1
18	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,-,-,6,-,9g,-,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	QHHSF	Other	75	1
19	Durum wheat	5,21,-,-,-,6,-,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	QHMSF	Other	86	1
20	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	QKCSF	Other	78	1
					79	1
21	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,-,-,6,8a,9g,-,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	QKHSF	Other	44	1
22	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,-,-,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	RCMTF	Other	73	1
23	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,-,-,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	RCRTF	Other	52	1
24	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,-,8a,9g,36,-,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	RFPTF	Other	77	1
25	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,-,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	RFRSF	Other	24	1
26	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,6,-,9g,-,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	RHCTF	Other	81	1
27	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,6,-,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,24,-,-,38,McN	RH RTP	Other	43	1
28	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,24,-,38,McN	RKRSP	Other	47	1
29	Bread Wheat	5,21,-,7b,11,6,-,9g,-,9b,-,-,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	RRLTC	Other	97	1
30	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,-,-,-,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	SFRSF	Other	76	1
31	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,-,-,6,-,9g,-,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,-,-,-,38,McN	SHHSF	Other	65	1
32	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,-,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	THRTC	Other	96	1
33	Durum wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,-,-,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	TKMTF	Other	51	1
34	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,-,30,17,9a,9d,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	TKPTF	Other	26	1
35	Bread Wheat	5,21,9e,7b,-,6,8a,9g,36,9b,-,17,9a,-,10,Tmp,-,-,-,38,McN	TKRPF	Other	54	1
Total						53

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738 **Table 8.** Seedling response of European wheat varieties to three isolates representing prevalent races
739 of *P. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* in Europe, a race from a recombining population in Spain, a race from the
740 German outbreak 2013, and two races representing Ug99 from East Africa.

	Common clades/races (2016-21)			Spain 2019	Germany 2013	Ug99	
	Clade III- B	Clade IV- B	Clade IV- F	unnamed	Clade VIII	Clade I	
Response category*	TTRTF	TKTTF	TKKTF	SKGBR	RFCNC	TTKTT	TTKSK
Susceptible	38	40	38	10	15	48	46
Intermediate	8	2	3	10	16	4	0

Re-emergence of stem rust in Europe

Resistant	8	11	12	33	21	2	8
Total number	54	53	53	53	52	54	54

*Varieties with IT responses below 2+ were categorized 'resistant', IT 2+ and 3- were considered 'intermediate' and lines with ITs of 3 and above were 'susceptible'.

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